

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

EXPLORING THE INTERNATIONAL COMMUNICATION OF CHINESE LANGUAGE AND THE EXPANSION OF THE CHINESE LANGUAGE LEARNER GROUP FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF CHINESE LANGUAGE LEARNING MOTIVATION

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Abstract

This article elaborates on the important significance of stimulating Chinese learning motivation for the international dissemination of Chinese language, discusses the relationship between expanding the international use of Chinese language, improving Chinese teaching efficiency, and stimulating and maintaining Chinese learning motivation, and puts forward several suggestions on how to make Chinese more useful and easier to learn.

Keywords: language communication, international dissemination of Chinese language, motivation for learning Chinese language, international cross-cultural communication.

This article will start from how to stimulate the motivation of foreign language learners to learn Chinese, explore the strategies for international dissemination of Chinese, and aim to illustrate that the primary task of international dissemination of Chinese is to continuously expand the group of Chinese learners. To expand the group of Chinese learners, it is necessary to be able to stimulate people's motivation to learn Chinese, and the key to stimulating Chinese learning motivation is how to make Chinese useful and easy to learn for learners. On this basis, this article proposes several ideas and suggestions on how to make Chinese useful and easy to learn.

1、 International dissemination of Chinese language and the expansion of the group of Chinese language learners

Language dissemination refers to the increase in the number of people who master and use a certain language, as well as the expansion of the scope of language use. Usually refers to the spread of a language from its native speakers to other populations, which can occur within a multi-ethnic country, such as the spread of Chinese among ethnic minorities in China; It can also occur across borders in other countries, such as the spread of English around the world. The former is the internal dissemination of language, while the latter is the external dissemination of language or the international dissemination of language. The current concept of "international promotion of Chinese language" refers to the external dissemination or international dissemination of Chinese language.

The degree and scale of dissemination of a language mainly depend on two factors: first, the number and distribution range of non-native language learners of the language; second, the size of the actual and potential uses of the language and the breadth of its application areas. These two factors are mutually causal and complementary: the more non-native language learners there are and the wider their distribution, the greater the usefulness of a language, because the more learners and the wider their distribution, the more opportunities they have to use this language for communication; The

greater the use of a language, the more learners it will be, as learners can gain more benefits from mastering the language. But in terms of logic and practical order, learning and mastery are prerequisites for use. Without learners and masters, the use of a language cannot be discussed. In this sense, how to stimulate the learning motivation of foreign language learners and make more foreign language learners willing to pay the cost of time, energy, and money to learn and master Chinese is the first issue that people who hope to effectively promote the international dissemination of Chinese must seriously consider.

The process of language dissemination often refers to the dissemination of culture and ideas. National language is an important carrier of national culture and concepts, and some people (William von Humboldt, 1997:50,70) believe that national language is the national spirit, and the national spirit is the national language. When a language spreads outward, the ethnic culture and ideas it carries and contains will also spread accordingly. Moreover, compared with other forms of cultural output, the dissemination of culture and ideas through language as a medium is more natural, more prone to subtle influence, and less likely to provoke resentment and resistance. Since the dissemination of this culture and concept is carried out through language dissemination, attracting more foreign language learners to learn this language naturally becomes its primary condition. Without this condition, culture and concepts cannot be transmitted to other populations on their own. In the current situation, no matter how much people emphasize that "international promotion of Chinese language" is not just a language issue, and no matter how rich the connotation is given to "international promotion of Chinese language", this "promotion" should not be separated from the platform and carrier of international dissemination of Chinese language. Therefore, for the rich connotation of "international promotion of Chinese language", continuously expanding the group of Chinese language learners is also a top priority.

From the above discussion, it is not difficult to see that the concepts of international dissemination and promotion of Chinese language are both related to and

significantly different from traditional teaching of Chinese as a foreign language. The core issue of teaching Chinese as a foreign language is language teaching; The international dissemination of Chinese language not only needs to solve the teaching problems of Chinese language, but also needs to adopt appropriate strategies and measures to expand the group of Chinese language learners and continuously expand the application fields of Chinese language in international communication. These tasks are not fully covered by the concept of teaching Chinese as a foreign language. However, teaching Chinese as a foreign language undoubtedly plays an important role in the international dissemination of Chinese language. Without a large number of qualified teachers for teaching Chinese as a foreign language, high-quality Chinese textbooks that are suitable for various foreign language learners, and the inability to effectively improve the level and efficiency of Chinese language teaching, all predetermined goals for international dissemination and promotion of Chinese language will be difficult to achieve smoothly.

2、 The Expansion of the Chinese Language Learner Group and the Stimulation of Chinese Language Learning Motivation

Language dissemination is a social phenomenon, and the degree of openness, international status, economic development, technological development, and cultural influence of a country or nation to the outside world are the ultimate determining factors for whether and to what extent a language can be disseminated. But we should also recognize that language learning and use are human actions, and without humans, there is no existence of language, let alone the spread of language. Undoubtedly, the dissemination of language is closely related to factors such as politics, economy, technology, and culture. However, only when these macro level factors affect human behavior can they play a practical role in the process of language dissemination.

Human behavior is always triggered by certain reasons, which include both external factors and internal motivation. Motivation is the psychological process or subjective factor that drives people to engage in a certain behavioral activity, and it is the internal driving force behind the implementation of a certain behavioral activity. The acquisition of a foreign language is different from the acquisition of native language ability. The acquisition of native language ability is not a conscious learning process, but a natural formation process. The acquisition of a foreign language, especially for adults, usually involves a conscious and proactive learning process, and the initiation and continuation of this learning process are driven by specific learning motivations. Therefore, the key to expanding the group of Chinese language learners is to stimulate the learning motivation of foreign language learners and maintain this motivation. Specifically, the stimulation and maintenance of learning motivation for Chinese language learners have the following important significance for the international dissemination of Chinese language:

Firstly, the emergence of motivation for learning Chinese is a necessary condition for the international

dissemination of Chinese language. Language dissemination begins with foreign language learners learning the language, and without institutional pressure, foreign language learning is optional rather than mandatory for an individual; Even if foreign language learning is mandatory, learning a certain language may still be optional rather than mandatory. Just as other behaviors of the same person are governed by specific motivations, foreign language learning behavior is also triggered by specific motivations. Therefore, whether people have the willingness to learn and master a certain language, whether they can generate sufficient motivation to learn the language, and under certain conditions, determine whether the language may be spread among a certain population.

Secondly, the strength of motivation for learning Chinese is related to the effectiveness of international language dissemination. Psychological research has shown that the effectiveness of human behavioral activities depends on the level of the actor's abilities and the strength of their motivation. But in a sense, motivation is more important than ability. For a specific person, their abilities are fixed over a certain period of time and will not undergo significant changes. Under the condition that ability is constant, the effectiveness of behavioral activities depends on the strength of motivation. Researchers in foreign language acquisition generally believe that the strength of learning motivation is an important factor in determining the success or failure of foreign language learning. Without sufficient motivation, even the most language gifted learners find it difficult to achieve the expected foreign language learning goals. As mentioned earlier, since learning and mastering a language is a prerequisite for using it, if a language does not have a certain number of successful learners among foreign language learners, it is impossible for the language to gain any practical status in international communication.

3、 The Motivation of Learning Chinese and the Useful and Easy Learning of Chinese

Social psychology believes that motivation and needs are closely related. Necessity is the thirst and desire for something that arises from the lack of it, and the satisfaction of the pursuit of desire is the universal motivation that inspires people to take action. Therefore, necessity is the underlying reason for behavioral activities. Motivation is derived from needs and is the direct cause of behavioral activities. Due to a lack of water in the body, people may have a need to drink water, which in turn can be transformed into a motivation to seek drinking water. When a person feels lonely, there is a need to interact with others, which in turn transforms into a motivation to reunite with family or talk to friends. If a language can become an effective tool to meet people's needs, acquiring the ability to use that language will become a human need, and this need will be transformed into a motivation to learn and master that language. The more needs a language can satisfy and the more useful it is, the more urgent people's need for it, and the stronger their motivation to learn and master it. A survey report from China on the motivation of foreign students to learn Chinese shows that their motivation to learn Chinese is based on some practical

material or spiritual needs. According to these survey reports, there are two main types of motivation for foreign students to learn Chinese: instrumental motivation and integrative motivation. The former aims to use Chinese to gain certain material benefits, such as hoping to obtain better job positions and easier opportunities for promotion after mastering Chinese; The latter aims to use Chinese to obtain certain spiritual enjoyment or satisfy the desire for knowledge, with the hope of satisfying one's interest in Chinese culture, art, or society after mastering Chinese.

Motivation is derived from the need for transformation, but this transformation is influenced by the external environment. When people have a certain need and there is more than one specific goal provided by the external environment that can meet the needs, the generation of motivation has strong selectivity. This selectivity is manifested in: among multiple specific goals that can meet the needs, people often choose the most beneficial and useful goals for themselves as the direction of their behavioral activities. When people are prepared to learn a foreign language for the sake of international communication, they often face such choices. If there are several languages that can meet the needs of foreign language learners, people often choose the language that best meets their own needs to learn. So the more useful a language is, the more likely it is to win in competition with other languages and become the target of choice for more foreign language learners.

From an economic perspective, people always hope to obtain maximum benefits with the minimum cost in the process of meeting their needs. Foreign language learning is a highly utilitarian behavior, where people mostly learn a foreign language for practical gain rather than just for entertainment. Because learning a foreign language comes at a cost, just like buying a commodity. However, purchasing a regular commodity only requires money, and acquiring a foreign language proficiency requires a considerable amount of time, effort, and hard work. Just as people always hope for good quality and affordable prices when purchasing goods, they also weigh the ratio of cost and benefit when choosing which language to learn. If the cost of learning is significantly greater than the benefits of learning, people often hold a negative attitude towards learning this language; Only when the learning benefits are significantly greater than the learning costs, will more people hold a positive attitude towards learning this language. It can be seen that in order to make more foreign language learners willing to learn Chinese, it is necessary to maintain the ratio between the cost and benefit of learning Chinese within the range that foreign language learners may accept. To maintain a reasonable ratio between learning costs and benefits, we need to expand the use of Chinese in international communication and continuously improve the learning benefits of learners; On the one hand, it is necessary to find ways to reduce the difficulty of learning Chinese, make it easier to learn, and strive to reduce the learning cost for learners.

4. Actively expanding the international use of Chinese language

How to make Chinese more useful, in general, is the issue of how to strive for more discourse power for Chinese in international communication and affairs; From a small perspective, it is the issue of how to enable foreign language learners of Chinese to gain more benefits. The wider and more significant the discourse power of a language, the more substantial the investment returns that foreign language learners may receive.

The acquisition of discourse power in a language is certainly based on the national strength in areas such as economy, technology, culture, politics, and military. The size of discourse power is always roughly equivalent to the comprehensive national strength, technological level, and international status of a country. However, we should also recognize that the acquisition of discourse power is not entirely a natural process in international trade. The advantageous position in academic exchange and other aspects does not necessarily lead to the widespread dissemination of a language. As some Western scholars (Stanley Lieberson, 2001) have analyzed, even if a country is an important trading partner of other countries, its language may not necessarily become the object that these countries need to learn and master, because communication between countries can be carried out through a common mastery of another language.

In the process of language dissemination, human subjective efforts are not completely idle. Within the limits allowed by objective conditions, the state adopts active language dissemination policies, implements proactive language dissemination plans, and can accelerate and promote the acquisition of dialogue language rights. In the process of English replacing French as the most widely used language internationally, Britain and the United States adopted an active English dissemination policy, investing a large amount of funds to promote English worldwide. Taking the UK as an example, as early as 1934, the UK established a special agency to promote English overseas - the British Council. The council's budget from 1989 to 1990 reached 321 million pounds. By 1994, the council had branches in 86 countries and established 55 English teaching centers in 32 countries. As Robert Philipson (2001) pointed out, English was only a minor language in 1600, but it developed into an important language for international communication in less than four centuries. This can be attributed to the great success of Britain in warfare, colonization, and trade in the 17th, 18th, and 19th centuries, as well as the military power and technological alliance position of the United States after World War II; On the other hand, the international dissemination of English also benefits from the huge investment made by British and American governments and individuals in promoting English.

Although China still needs long-term efforts to become an economic and technological powerhouse, in terms of current national strength, China has become the fourth largest economy in the world. The country's international status has significantly improved, and foreign exchanges in trade, culture, and other aspects are unprecedentedly active. The rapidly developing China is attracting more and more attention, which has created

favorable objective conditions for accelerating the international dissemination of the Chinese language. In the face of such development opportunities, we should fully utilize the potential space provided by China's development for the dissemination of Chinese language. Through active language dissemination strategies and enterprising work, we should gradually transform the potential space for Chinese language dissemination into tangible Chinese discourse power. Otherwise, the achievements that could have been actively fought for or achieved may be lost in vain.

From the perspective of language communication strategies, increasing the frequency and level of use of a language in international communication will stimulate potential learners' needs for the language. We can start from these two aspects, actively expand the international use of bilingualism, expand the demand for Chinese, promote the international dissemination of Chinese, and gradually make Chinese an important language in international communication.

(1) Continuously increasing the frequency of using Chinese

To continuously improve the frequency of using Chinese in international communication, the first issue to be addressed is attitude and conceptual issues, that is, whether we can all confidently demand the use of Chinese under objective conditions. The actual situation seems to be different. In 2004, domestic news media extensively reported on the ban of Chinese language at the Fourth Global Chinese Physicists Conference. At this conference held in Shanghai with all Chinese attendees, English was designated as the only working language, while Chinese was banned. Even proposals to adopt bilingual English and Chinese were rejected by conference organizers citing international conventions. This matter is quite representative in today's China, where English is considered an important tool for aligning with the international community. If we blindly adhere to so-called international conventions and automatically give up the right to use Chinese in the game of discourse power, the result will only be self-destructive of the future of international dissemination of Chinese. Therefore, we hope that Chinese people can enhance their awareness of using Chinese in international communication, fully utilize the advantageous position brought about by China's economic development and international status enhancement, and gradually strive for greater space for the use of Chinese language when conditions permit. As for specific strategies, we suggest:

1. Strive to make Chinese the working language or one of the working languages in more domestic international conferences and international conferences with Chinese as the main body, and gradually strive to make Chinese one of the working languages in various overseas international conferences;

2. Strive to make Chinese the working language in more international business negotiations;

3. Strive to enable more Chinese academic journals to enter international academic publication retrieval systems such as SCI, SSCI, and AHCI;

4. Strengthen the standardization of Chinese scientific and technological terminology, so that Chinese

can better adapt to the development of science and technology today;

5. Building a comprehensive database based on the international internet and using Chinese as a carrier, continuously increasing the proportion of Chinese resources in the virtual space;

6. Gradually expand the global coverage of Chinese radio and television programs;

7. Encourage book publishing companies to actively explore the overseas market of Chinese books and continuously increase the overseas circulation of Chinese books.

(2) Gradually improving the level of use of Chinese language

In international communication, if a language is only used in the daily activities of the general public and cannot enter higher-level communication fields, it is difficult to become an important language in the international community. In today's world, the reason why English holds such an important position is not only because it has high universality in various fields of international communication, but also because it has unparalleled advantages in areas that are crucial for both national and individual development, such as international politics, international trade, international finance, technology, academia, etc. If a language is limited to low-end use, even if it reaches a higher frequency of use, its role in international dissemination is limited. Therefore, in the process of international dissemination of Chinese, more attention and more active promotion should be given to the high-end use of Chinese. The various aspects involved in our suggestions mentioned above belong to the high-end field of language use. Actively expanding the scope of Chinese language use and continuously improving the frequency of Chinese language use in these fields is undoubtedly of great significance for accelerating the international dissemination of Chinese language.

5. Strive to improve the efficiency of Chinese language teaching

How to make Chinese easier to learn, the core issue is how to enable more foreign language learners who have never learned Chinese to better master Chinese in a shorter period of time through efficient Chinese language teaching. A native English speaker naturally finds it difficult to learn French or German when learning Chinese, which is determined by the historical homology and differences between languages, and cannot be changed by human effort. All we can do is try to improve the efficiency of Chinese language teaching, so that learners can acquire Chinese communication skills with as little learning cost as possible. Chinese is considered one of the most difficult languages to learn in the world (Xu Daming, Tao Hongyin, Xie Tianwei, 1997:165). If we cannot reduce the difficulty and cost of learning Chinese within the possible range, learners may develop a fear of difficulty, their learning motivation and confidence may be shaken, and the international dissemination of Chinese will inevitably be hindered to a certain extent.

The key to improving the efficiency of Chinese language teaching is to solve the problems of what to

teach and how to teach. Although there may be different opinions on these issues, one thing should be certain: the resolution of these issues should be subject to the teaching objectives of teaching Chinese as a foreign language. Our teaching objective should be clear, which is to enable more foreign language learners who have never learned Chinese to master it more easily in the shortest possible time. This is also one of the most fundamental goals of international dissemination of Chinese language.

In order to achieve the teaching objectives of teaching Chinese as a foreign language, we believe that the following aspects should be given attention and importance:

(1) Strengthening the Research on Chinese Ontology for Teaching Chinese as a Foreign Language

What we mean by Chinese ontology research for teaching Chinese as a foreign language is not a completely different research field from general language ontology research, but rather a Chinese ontology research that is problem oriented, fully considers teaching needs, targeted, and not solely based on academic interests. Only by strengthening such research can we make our teaching content more suitable for the needs of foreign language learners, better answer their questions and improve their learning efficiency. In this type of research, we believe that the comparative study of Chinese and foreign languages and the comprehensive study of grammar rules should be given attention.

1. Comparative Study between Chinese and Foreign Languages

In the process of foreign language learning, learners' mother tongue can interfere, and the differences between the target language and mother tongue often lead to negative transfer, which is one of the main reasons for learners to make errors. In teaching Chinese as a foreign language, the difficulties for foreign language learners to learn Chinese are often related to the differences between foreign languages and Chinese. (Long Qingran, 1990; Zheng Yide, 1995; Lu Jianming, 2000) Therefore, understanding the similarities and differences between Chinese and foreign languages is of great significance for Chinese language teaching. However, as of now, research in this area seems to be relatively weak, with limited available results and even fewer systematic comparisons. Moreover, the scope of comparative research is relatively narrow, with less or even less involvement in important languages such as Russian, French, German, Spanish, Arabic, etc. (Li Quan, 2006; Ding Chongming, 2006) This situation clearly cannot meet the current need to accelerate the international dissemination of Chinese language.

2. Comprehensive research on grammar rules

At present, research on Chinese grammar is constantly refining, with increasingly detailed rules and more subcategories of parts of speech. This is undoubtedly necessary for deepening people's understanding of Chinese. But if there is only analysis without synthesis, only refinement without summarization, some fundamental and global grammar rules will not be easily discovered. According to our incomplete statistics, between 2004 and 2005, there were over 360 modern Chinese grammar research papers published in official

domestic journals each year. Based on this quantity, the total number of officially published modern Chinese grammar research papers in China should be over 10000 so far. What are the specific grammar rules proposed in these 10000 papers? How many subcategories of parts of speech should be separated? Nevertheless, people still believe that the current grammar rules are not detailed enough, as these rules still cannot completely seal the errors produced by Chinese learners. This view may be correct, but from another perspective, this phenomenon may indicate the limitations of research that emphasizes analysis over synthesis, and the resulting rules may not have enough explanatory power. From a teaching perspective, the number of rules with strong explanatory power and wide applicability is limited, making them easier to learn and master. Once mastered, their usefulness will also be greater. However, rules that can only explain individual grammatical phenomena are bound to be numerous. If these rules are isolated from each other and lack systematic connections, learners will face enormous pressure to learn and master them. So whether from the perspective of Chinese ontology research or improving the efficiency of teaching Chinese as a foreign language, we should consciously strengthen the comprehensive study of Chinese grammar rules, and try to explain systematic grammar phenomena with more general rules as much as possible.

(2) Promoting the improvement and refinement of teaching concepts

Teaching philosophy refers to teaching ideas or concepts (Zhao Jinming, 2007), the teaching philosophy of teaching Chinese as a foreign language. According to our understanding, its core content should be a theoretical understanding of the teaching objectives and methods of teaching Chinese as a foreign language. However, teaching philosophy is not a specific teaching objective and method itself, but a theoretical principle based on which different teaching objectives and methods are evaluated and screened. The specific objects of teaching are different, and the teaching objectives and methods to achieve these objectives often vary. However, different teaching objectives and methods can adhere to the same teaching philosophy. Teaching philosophy should have a high theoretical content and reach a high level of generalization. Only in this way can teaching philosophy have broad guiding significance in complex and diverse teaching practices, and this guiding significance is the main reason why we value teaching philosophy.

In recent years, scholars (Zhao Jinming, 2007) have conducted in-depth summaries of the historical development of teaching Chinese as a foreign language and provided their own interpretations of some important language teaching concepts. We believe this is a very beneficial work. The practice of teaching Chinese as a foreign language in our country has gone through more than half a century, which has condensed the experience and wisdom of several generations. Now, on the one hand, we need to summarize, refine, and elevate these valuable practical experiences based on the general theories of linguistics, education, and

psychology. On the other hand, we need to pay attention to the development of the teaching philosophy of teaching Chinese as a foreign language in the world, especially in other countries. With a broad mind that embraces all rivers, we can learn from and draw useful elements from it, continuously improve and perfect our teaching philosophy. Only in this way can all practices of teaching Chinese as a foreign language be guided by advanced teaching concepts, and the effectiveness and efficiency of teaching Chinese as a foreign language be fundamentally guaranteed.

(3) Exploration of Strengthening Teaching Methods

Teaching methods are crucial for language teaching, and different teaching methods may result in significant differences in teaching effectiveness. Therefore, strengthening the research and exploration of teaching methods is of great significance for improving the efficiency of teaching Chinese as a foreign language. At present, people's understanding of the laws of foreign language acquisition is still very limited, and it is unclear what kind of teaching method is the most effective. In this situation, innovation and exploration of teaching methods should be encouraged, and various attempts and experiments should be conducted. Comparison is the key to identification. Only through continuous exploration and experimentation can we discover truly effective teaching methods.

In the exploration of teaching methods, we believe that the issue of the relationship between knowledge and ability is worth serious consideration. From the user's perspective, language is an ability, and mastering a language means being able to rely on intuition, that is, language sense, rather than rational analysis for encoding and decoding. It is based on this understanding of the nature of language that people generally believe that Chinese language classes for foreigners should be a skill course aimed at cultivating language ability, rather than a theoretical and knowledge course. However, what are the effective ways to acquire language ability? How can we achieve the teaching goal of cultivating language ability while minimizing learning costs to the greatest extent possible? People's understanding of this is not consistent, and we will only take grammar as an example. One viewpoint holds that in teaching Chinese as a foreign language, grammar knowledge is not important, and strengthening listening and reading to acquire a large amount of sensory knowledge is the most important way to develop language ability; Another viewpoint holds that learning grammar knowledge is an effective method for mastering a language, and grammar teaching should play an important role in teaching Chinese as a second language. (Zhao Jinming, 2002) These two perspectives may each have their own reasons, or they may each adapt to different levels of learners. However, rational knowledge does not equate to ability. Some basic grammar rules may need to be taught, but how to teach them is beneficial for learners to develop language ability or sense, which should be carefully studied. The accumulation of sensory knowledge to form language ability essentially relies on the learner's own language induction ability to acquire language rules, and this induction process is also

the process of forming language sense. But in terms of learning efficiency, can moderate teaching of grammar knowledge guide and assist learners in their induction? If the teaching of grammar knowledge can play such a role, then to what extent is it moderate? These issues also require careful study. We suggest conducting comparative teaching experiments on the questions raised here, and believe that these teaching experiments will be helpful in seeking answers to the questions.

(4) Solve the problem of cultural introduction well

Verbal communication always occurs in specific social contexts and is constrained by them. Cultural factors are an important component of social contexts. Therefore, the use of language, including speech comprehension and expression, is inevitably influenced and constrained by specific cultural backgrounds. Due to the close relationship between language proficiency and cognitive level of relevant cultures, the issue of cultural introduction in teaching Chinese as a foreign language has always received widespread attention since the 1990s.

"Culture" is a comprehensive category, and due to the needs of language teaching, many people advocate distinguishing between cultural factors that directly affect cross-cultural communication and those that do not. Some people refer to the former as "communicative culture". According to the existing discussions on communicative culture, its basic content is the specific cultural connotations of language forms and pragmatic conventions based on specific cultures. Therefore, some people also refer to it as "semantic culture" and "pragmatic culture". (Chen Guanglei, 1992) In fact, these cultural factors themselves are an important component of human language ability, and therefore should certainly become an important teaching content in teaching Chinese as a foreign language. The problem is that Chinese Chinese language teachers have long been accustomed to these cultural factors of their own ethnic group and do not feel that they (at least a considerable part of them) have any special features, so they cannot be keenly aware of their special significance to foreign language learners. To solve this problem of neglect, it is necessary to conduct comparative analysis and research on communication cultures between China and foreign countries. If we can organize a group of scholars who are familiar with both Chinese and foreign communication cultures to conduct comprehensive and targeted analysis and research on the similarities and differences between Chinese and foreign communication cultures, the results obtained will have a wide range of positive effects on classroom teaching of Chinese as a foreign language and textbook development.

From previous discussions, the focus of attention on cultural introduction in teaching Chinese as a foreign language has always been on so-called communicative cultures that may lead to cross-cultural communication barriers. Many scholars believe that cultural introduction should be related to cultivating students' language communication abilities. (Lu Jianji, 1990; Xu Jiazhen, 2000) If we only look at language teaching from a simple perspective, this view is undoubtedly reasonable. However, if we look at the historical mission of "international promotion of Chinese language"

and only emphasize the introduction of "small cultures" such as communicative culture, while ignoring the dissemination of "big cultures" such as the worldview, values, and moral views of the Chinese nation, it may not be appropriate. Because the spread of any language is always accompanied by the spread of a "big culture", pure language dissemination never exists. We only need to look at the spread of Chinese characters in North Korea and Japan in history, as well as the spread of English around the world today, and it is easy to understand this. Of course, we do not advocate specifically teaching and promoting these cultural contents in the classroom of teaching Chinese as a foreign language. This completely detached cultural dissemination method is not in line with the concept of "international promotion of Chinese language" and may not necessarily achieve good results; We only advocate that there should be a conscious awareness of cultural dissemination in the process of teaching Chinese as a foreign language. In terms of the selection of texts and teaching content, we should incorporate and reflect the content of "big culture" in a way that is not propagated or instilled, so that foreign language learners can gradually appreciate the excellent culture of the Chinese nation in the process of learning Chinese.

(5) Compilation of Usage Reference Books

To do a good job, one must first sharpen their tools. A good Chinese reference book is a powerful tool for learning Chinese. At present, the main reference books we can provide to Chinese learners are grammar books and dictionaries. Grammar books explain the organization rules of sentences based on parts of speech (including subcategories), and their explanation of grammar functions only involves categorical words, without involving individual words (excluding virtual words); Dictionaries (excluding function word dictionaries) mainly explain the meaning of words rather than their usage, although the object of explanation is the individual words. From here, we can see that there is still a gap in the Chinese language knowledge provided by reference books, which is the usage of words. The usage of words mainly refers to the usage characteristics of words (including some solidified sentences) that are difficult to summarize and explain in class form. For example, some words have the same part of speech, but the words they can be paired with are not exactly the same, such as "see" and "see", "see" and "see", etc; Some language elements have been solidified, but due to their different forms from words, they are generally not included in dictionaries; Due to its unique usage and inability to generalize, grammar books do not cover the special meanings and usage of phrases such as "look at you", "look at me", "you're here again", "really", "really", etc.

These knowledge of usage and grammar are disregarded because they are too individualistic and often cannot or cannot be fully analogized, making it difficult to incorporate them into the grammar rule system; A general dictionary doesn't care because it mainly explains the meaning of words. If usage is also included, a considerable number of entries will have longer explanations, and the length of different entries will be

extremely uneven, which is a taboo in dictionary compilation. People often say that teaching foreigners Chinese grammar is easy to understand and easy to use, and this mistake is often due to improper vocabulary. Grammar can only provide the skeleton of sentences, and the details of word selection are not discussed. Grammar is generally not taught in the classroom (because it cannot be taught completely). In this situation, if there are no reference books available for searching, learners can only explore on their own. If this situation is not changed, it is obviously very unfavorable for learners to master the details of Chinese usage rules. If we can strengthen the research on word usage and write usage reference books for foreign learners, it is equivalent to providing learners with an extracurricular teacher in Chinese usage, which is undoubtedly very beneficial for improving their learning efficiency.

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